

THEORY AND PRACTICE OF IMPLEMENTING BLENDED LEARNING IN ENGLISH LESSONS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6353931>

Khodjimatova Albina Askarovna

English lecturer Westminster International
University in Tashkent

Abstract: The phenomenon of such technology as Blended Learning in the conditions of modern information society is really relevant. This technology is the most suitable for teaching English because it allows the teacher to combine the forms of offline and online learning, and motivates students to achieve maximum results. The difficulty lies in the fact that this technology is a new learning technology, therefore teachers working on the implementation of this model in the process of teaching English should have a reasonable understanding of the theoretical aspects and an understanding of the existing practices of the Blended Learning model. This article discusses the theoretical aspects of this process and provides an overview of the existing practices for implementing the Blended Learning model. It should be noted that this material can be advantageous for both theoretical and practical use.

Key words: blended learning, offline and online format, technology, Internet, traditional and innovative learning, English.

Introduction

Innovations in the process of teaching a foreign language affect a variety of aspects of the educational process, including changing the organization of space in classrooms, equipping classrooms with modern technical means, experimenting with new educational technologies both in the classroom and during self-study of high school, lyceum and college students. Currently used methods of teaching foreign languages involve the active use of various information technologies that ensure accessibility, openness and mobility of the educational process.

In terms of the positive process of educational computerization, modern teaching methods have gradually transitioned from traditional educational forms to e-learning, accompanied by new teaching methods actively introduced in the teaching process. The process of introducing computer technologies into education dates back to the mid-1980s. This is mainly due to the development of information and communication technologies and the information processing of society. In 1999, new software was released in the United States, which made it possible to conduct lessons using the Internet environment. This event led to the formation of the term “blended learning”.

The introduction of blended learning seemed impossible to us not so long ago. We could not even imagine that this technology would be so relevant in modern conditions. To date, almost every teacher has managed to work in different modes - offline and online formats, and it is worth noting that the latter is becoming more and more relevant. It provides a lot of professional opportunities for both the teacher and students in terms of

personal development, and therefore, this technology deserves special attention. [1; p. 154]

Blended learning is a modern, universal educational technology that combines both traditional and digital forms of learning and meets the individual requirements of both teachers and learners. Learning is considered blended if from 30% to 79% of the study time is spent online. [2; p.5] In other words, a new educational environment is being created where a student's learning experience is facilitated by a teacher. The technology of blended learning is based on the principle of interactivity, which allows the teacher to organize training in such a way that students are maximally involved in the process of active communication and interested in learning English. [3; p.27-32] Blended learning has a number of advantages to make the foreign language teaching process as effective as possible, as it combines formal (classwork, written assignments, group and partner work, questioning) and informal learning tools (online-platforms, mobile applications, videoconferencing) that allow to optimize the workflow not only in terms of learning tools, but also in terms of the organization of working time and space, which make it possible to organize the educational process at a convenient time and space for both the teacher and the students. [4; p.145]

Blended learning is a combination of face-to-face, online and distance learning. It should be noted that blended learning does not mean a complete rejection of traditional offline education, since it contributes to the formation of the most important language and socio-cultural skills. [5; c.578]

Distinctive features of Blended Learning

An analysis of the literature dealing with the implementation and use of blended learning gives us the opportunity to highlight some of its distinctive features, namely:

- Changing the traditional paradigm of teacher-student relationships

When implementing the blended learning model, the teacher performs several roles at once, the most important of which is the role of *a tutor* - the so-called assistant and advisor to students. Also, the teacher is assigned the role of *an organizer* – s/he does not deliver the educational material him/herself, but organizes the process of receiving and studying it by students. The role of *a lecturer* allows the teacher to prepare, process educational materials in various forms, answer the students' questions about the subject matter and give additional advice on the most difficult topics, both offline and online;

- Developing independent learning skills

The basis of the educational process when implementing the blended learning model is the targeted, systematic, independent work of students, which is controlled by the teacher. Students can choose the place of study that is most convenient for them, using special teaching aids and the possibility of establishing contact with the teacher. It should be noted that blended learning maximally stimulates the formation of independent learning skills, information gathering, self-motivation and planning of one's own activities;

- Individual support of students' learning activities by a teacher both offline and online.

Considering this, as already mentioned, students can get additional advice on the most difficult issues and, with the help of a teacher, determine the individual course of their development.

The classification, which is generally accepted worldwide, identifies six models of blended learning; each of these models aims to meet different needs, achieve different goals. [6; p.1]

- The face-to-face driver model aims to reinforce traditional offline learning. The main volume of the educational program is determined by the teacher, if necessary, he also determines the need to switch to the online format, while the latter format is defined as an auxiliary format.

- The rotation model implies the alternation of traditional offline learning and independent work in an online format in an individual mode (work on special training sites, platforms, acquaintance with online information sources).

- The Flex model or the so-called flexible model mainly aims to work on the online platform of an educational organization, but depending on the needs, the teacher carries out either individual or group work offline.

- The Online Lab model is functionally similar to the Flex model, but implies the systematic delivery of an entire course flow within a specific topic. This model is implemented under the full guidance and control of the teacher and can also be combined with offline work if required.

- The Self-Blend model implies that students independently determine which of offline classes within a particular topic need to be supplemented with online classes.

- The online driver model implies online distance learning. In fact, offline classes can also be added to the course, but basically all learning is made remotely. [7; c.141]

Advantages and Disadvantages of Blended Learning

Introducing these models into the educational process has both advantages and disadvantages. [8; p.488]

The advantages of introducing blended learning models include automation of the learning process, the possibility of constant access to educational materials, systematic monitoring of the results of students' learning activities, student work at an individual pace and mode, and developing students' critical thinking skills. It is also worth noting that the introduction of blended learning makes it possible to include different types of auxiliary elements in the learning process - audio and video tools, charts, graphics, links to various resources, etc.

Despite many advantages, the blended learning model also has disadvantages. The disadvantages include the dependence of this type of education on many factors: the level of ICT literacy of teachers and students, the availability of computer equipment, a stable connection to the Internet. However, according to many experts involved in the introduction of this model into the educational process, all the above shortcomings can be addressed: ICT skills can be improved by training both the teacher and students in various technology courses and technical problems associated with the availability of the necessary equipment can be solved by entering into various educational support programs that will help to obtain the necessary funding to solve technical problems.

As already mentioned, the blended learning model is especially effective in the process of teaching English, as it provides the opportunity for live communication as part of offline learning, as well as working with the language online - reading various texts on specialized sites, watching educational videos, working in various language platforms. In other words, blended learning provides a wide range of opportunities for learning a foreign language, and the blended learning model should be driven by learners' needs and goals. [9; p.154]

Application of Blended Learning Models

Within the framework of existing models of blended learning, different methods, means and ways of learning are used. Some of them help develop just one of the language skills, while others allow you to improve all four language skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing. But in any case, the result of introducing blended learning will be indeed significant.

Thus, the rotation model is the strategy that is the easiest to implement in the process of foreign language teaching, since within its framework, students will be able to work at their level of language proficiency, thereby differentiating the whole learning process. So, one of the ways of learning within the framework of this model is the quest technology. The teacher thinks over a multi-station route that will include different tasks in English. Students must solve the tasks presented, as the solution obtained at one station is a clue for the next. Thus, the Alias game can be offered to the students, in which the student leader must explain as many words as possible in a short time so that his/her team can guess them, thereby expanding the vocabulary within a specific subject to be studied. Students may also be offered to watch videos or listen to audio recordings, followed by written assignments. The answers received are a cue to move on to the next station.

When introducing a model like Flex into the educational process, the teacher needs to understand that most of the information should be provided online, but in traditional school settings. This model offers great opportunities to implement a student-centered approach to pacing and content. It is advisable to use such a model when preparing for English exams.

The Face-to-face Driver model is a good option for classes where students have different abilities and skills. This model comes closest to traditional learning. The organization of online learning is possible, for example, for students who are behind in their studies in order to organize additional time for working on a specific topic. Thus, the teacher can conduct individual consultations for students with difficulties in learning grammar or words, and receive practical tasks for processing the difficulties encountered at home. The effectiveness of their work can be checked at home by the teacher in an online format: through Google tests or work on different platforms. This gives students the practice and extra time they need to master the material.

The Online Driver model, as mentioned earlier, is a complete distance learning course in an online format. In this case, students can independently study lexical and grammatical issues and practice listening and speaking, receiving the necessary advice and instructions from the teacher in an online format. As part of working on a topic, it would

be advisable for the teacher to arrange online interviews from time to time, which will have a positive effect on the formation of skills such as listening and speaking.

The teacher faces various difficulties when implementing the blended learning model, so some points need to be thought out in advance in order to facilitate the process of its implementation as much as possible.

First of all, the teacher must choose a platform for organizing remote support for the course of study. Such a platform can be e-mail, social networks, a blog, a platform on an educational platform (Moodle, Google Classroom, Smart-Learn, Yandex Class, Openclass, Edmodo). The choice should be made based on the technical capabilities of the students and their educational needs. On the chosen platform, the teacher can organize study groups and post assignments for them in the form of text files, video, audio. The higher the degree of interactivity of the organized educational process on the chosen platform, the more effective the training will be.

Secondly, the teacher must determine the basic resources for teaching: printed teaching materials, video lessons, and electronic textbooks. Resources must be available for students to work from home, i.e. available at home or available on the Internet.

Also, the teacher must necessarily establish certain rules of work for students within the framework of this model. So, it is possible to establish time limits on establishing contacts with a teacher, and there is a ban on the use of obscene language on online platforms. The rules should be established taking into account the personal characteristics of students and the framework established directly by the educational institution.

It is also worth noting that blended learning is a very labor-intensive form of organizing the educational process. The teacher must thoroughly prepare for the lessons, make route plans and instructions for each student, choose teaching materials that are appropriate to the learning goals, and develop their own methodological developments.

In addition, the teacher needs to take into account the psychological characteristics of students, their level of motivation and the formation of ICT competence. Moreover, the ability to organize oneself, individual educational needs and the speed and rhythm of mastering the subject matter play an important role. Also, the teacher should keep in mind that not all students are ready for this type of learning at this time. When introducing blended learning technology, the teacher must implement a differentiated approach and the teaching as a whole must comply with the concept of the activity approach and be aimed at obtaining a certain result. In this case, the teacher is a mentor, an assistant in completing tasks. [10; p. 235]

Blended learning technology can be considered a universal means of implementing the State Educational Standard in Uzbekistan. It is characterized by new educational opportunities, an individual educational path, and an active position of the student and, as a result, an increase in motivation for learning activities.

The blended form of teaching English has the character of a holistic educational process, consisting of two parts: active cognitive activity of students under the guidance and control of the teacher and in cooperation with other students and distance learning, in which various types of independent work predominate. Combining the best aspects and

advantages of teaching in the classroom, distance learning allows you to implement the principles of visibility, adaptability and convenience of working in large groups.

Conclusion

It is important to understand that blended learning means technologies, costs, a certain attitude of students and teachers. This is a large-scale introduction to the educational process, and it should not be a tribute to fashion, but a solution to specific goals; for example, increasing overall academic performance, educational level or technological literacy; automation of the process of assessing students' knowledge; formation of a special worldview that includes independence and the ability to learn.

Thanks to the introduction of the blended learning model, students get the opportunity to independently organize their own educational space, choose the direction towards realizing their potential, the level of mastering of subject matter and the ability to be responsible for their choices. The flexibility of the educational system, the ability to choose the place, time and speed of study solves the difficulties of mastering the subject material in case of missing classes. [11; p. 40] The teacher, in turn, has more opportunities to creatively shape the educational process. The boring moments of theoretical study, which require passive perception of the subject matter, disappear; the active involvement of the students becomes practice-oriented. Quizzes, language workshops, project activities, participation in language conferences – all kinds of formats for organizing educational work become possible, increasing the effectiveness of learning, involving students in the process of continuous education, motivating them to learn new things.

Thus, based on all of the above-mentioned, it can be concluded that the blended learning model is indeed the most relevant learning model today, and its use in teaching English can be considered fully appropriate.

References

1. Андреева Н.В. Шаг школы в смешанное обучение /Андреева Н.В., Рождественская Л.В., Ярмахов Б.Б.- М.: Национальная открытая школа, 2016, - 279 с.
2. Watwood B. Building from content to community: Rethinking the transition to online teaching and learning: A CTE White Paper / Britt Watwood, Jeffery Nugent, William “Bud” Deihl. – Virginia Commonwealth University: Center for teaching excellence, 2009.- p 5.
3. Вардашкина Е. В. Использование информационно-коммуникационных технологий в обучении английскому языку студентов неязыковых вузов // Инновации и современная наука: материалы международной заочной научно-практической конференции. Ч II. — Новосибирск, 2011. — С.27–32
4. Воронина, М. В. "Перевернутый" класс – инновационная модель обучения / М. В. Воронина // Открытое образование. – 2018. – Т. 22. – № 5. – С. 40-51. – DOI 10.21686/1818-4243-2018-5-40-51.
5. Кудряшова А. В., Горбатова Т. Н. Роли преподавателя в процессе развития творческой самостоятельности студентов высших учебных заведений // Молодой ученый. — 2015. — № 4. — С. 577–580.

6. Желнова Е. В. 8 этапов смешанного обучения (обзор статьи Д. Пентер Missed Steps). [Электронный ресурс]. — Режим доступа: <http://www.obs.ru/interest/publ/?thread=57>.
7. Костина Е. В. Модель смешанного обучения (Blended Learning) и ее использование в преподавании иностранных языков // Известия высших учебных заведений. Серия: Гуманитарные науки. 2010. Т. 1. № 2. С. 141–144.
8. Куркан, Н. В. Эффективность смешанного обучения при обучении иностранному языку в условиях современного образования / Н. В. Куркан. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2015. — № 5 (85). — С. 488-491. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/85/16008/> (дата обращения: 04.03.2022).
9. Кулиева, О. Н. Эффективное учебное видео: типы, дидактические функции, критерии / О. Н. Кулиева // Образование в 21-ом веке. – 2019. – № 1(1). – С. 154-163.
10. Современные технологии в науке и образовании - СТНО-2018 : Сборник трудов международного научно-технического форума: в 11 томах, Рязань, 28 февраля – 02 2018 года / Под общ. ред. О.В. Миловзорова. – Рязань: Рязанский государственный радиотехнический университет, 2018. – 234 с. – ISBN 978-5-7722-0301-9.
11. Руденок, Е. А. Создание информационно-коммуникационной среды как условие формирования образовательной автономии гимназистов (из опыта работы учителя) / Е. А. Руденок // Методист. – 2013. – № 9. – С. 40-51.